

Research

The impact of Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism on foreign direct investment flows in the Arab countries

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Abstract :Foreign direct investment is considered one of the main sources of any economy. Countries seek to attract foreign direct investment flows to them. This results in the improvement of the economy, the transfer of technology and the foreign currency of the host country and the provision of employment opportunities. The Arab countries are considered to suffer from the scarcity of foreign direct investment In this study, we studied the impact of political stability and the absence of violence on direct foreign investment flows. In the wake of the waves of protests that emerged in the so-called Arab Spring. These protests turned into violent waves of violence and terrorism, which led to the low economic level of these countries, including foreign direct investment flows. Our study shows that foreign direct investment flows to Arab countries are concentrated in those countries that enjoy political stability, security and financial abundance, and are lower in poor countries and those suffering from waves of violence and political instability.

1. Introduction

Previously Metwally et al. (M.M. Metwally,1989) (1) examined some factors affecting FDI flows in three Arab countries: Egypt, Jordan and the Sultanate of Oman, and concluded that there is a relationship between economic growth and FDI flows to these countries, as (Omran, Mohammed and Ali Bolbol ,2003)(2) conclusions that emerge from their paper are that domestic financial reforms should precede policies promoting FDI, investment measures should enhance the environment for all investors—foreign and domestic alike—and liberal commercial policies should be designed as initial measures to attract FDI. (Haico Ebbers ,2006) (3) When he tested

the determinants of foreign direct investment (FDI) into countries of the Middle East North Africa (MENA) region, He based on an econometric model that includes factors that potentially drive FDI flows into countries in the MENA region, he found Energy endowments have a negative impact on FDI flows into a country.

GDP per capita, openness to trade and oil prices have a positive impact on FDI inflows, while aggregate measures of environmental risk are not a differentiating factor among countries in the region, Energy endowments have a negative impact on FDI flows into a country, (Signe Krogstrup,2006),⁴ told from a welfare perspective, costly financial incentives to attract FDI are only justified if FDI exhibits positive growth externalities.

The recent empirical literature shows, however, that FDI may also have negative externalities, depending on the level of absorptive capacity for FDI of the host country, (SUFIAN ELTAYEB MOHAMED AND MOISE and SIDIROPOULOS ,2010) (5) The paper concludes that, countries that are receiving fewer foreign investments could make themselves more attractive to potential foreign investors. So, the policy makers in the MENA region should remove all barriers to trade, develop their financial system and build appropriate institutions. (KAMAL A. EL-WASSAL 2012) (6) found that the impact of FDI on economic growth in Arab countries is limited or negligible. The findings also suggest that financial development, trade openness, human capital and infrastructure quality are not significantly improving Arab countries' (Alamedin Bannaga at.el 2013) (7) assesses the effects of governance on foreign direct investment inflows in Arab countries using panel regression based on an augmented gravity model. The regression results lend a strong support for the significance of good governance to foreign direct investment inflows.(Heba E. Helmy,2013) (8) The paper investigates the link between corruption and FDI flows to the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) and assesses whether or not corruption has more importance than other FDI determinants.

By employing several panel settings with various econometric specifications on 21 MENA countries over the period 2003 to 2009, it is demonstrated that FDI varies positively with corruption. Additionally, FDI in MENA was found to vary positively with per capita income, openness, freedom and security of investments and negatively with the tax and homicide rates. (Sherif Abbas and , Dalia El Mosallamy 2016) (9) . their findings would be of use to market participants, regulators and policy makers as they support the view arguing that MENA region is an important trade hub and thus should remove all trade barriers and restrictions to capitalize on

their strategic location in the world to facilitate trade to Europe Africa and Asia.(Omar F and Bizri 2018) (10) ,they underline the need of the Arab countries for STI inputs in order to tackle the multitude of challenges they face with regard to diversifying their economies creating employment opportunities, as well as combatting poverty, environmental degradation, and dwindling resources. As one of its conclusions, this author's considers predominance of rentiers in governance systems a root cause of many ills suffered by Arab socioeconomic development. Although difficult to dismantle, such models should be amenable to earnest and persistent efforts in economic policy making and subsequent action, favoring socioeconomic development at local community levels.

Most different developed and developing countries in the world have a strong interest in foreign investment. Developing countries are also showing increasing interest in foreign investment because they lack stable financial resources on the one hand and lack technology on the other.

Foreign direct investment inflows into the Arab countries are about 8%, compared with 20% of the world's population, which reflects the need for some Arab markets to further open up FDI inflows. The legal environment, as an important factor affecting these investment inflows, also needs to be continuously strengthened in some Arab countries. At the same time, other factors such as the availability of skilled labor, market size and economic openness need to be improved. Per capita GDP, laws and subsidiary regulations, promotion and commercialization of the popular Arab trade area also have an impact on the value fluctuations of foreign direct investment flows into Arab countries each year. However, there are few studies on the effects of political stability and non-violence factors on the flow of direct investment in Arab countries, especially the impact of this factor on the huge fluctuations between Arab countries and countries, especially Yemen, Egypt, which have experienced the "Arab Spring" , Libya, Syria, and Tunisia, most of these countries have experienced multiple political stability issues, or there is violence and terrorism, and some countries are suffering from constant violence, such as Egypt, Somalia, Tunisia, and others. In the early stages of regional policy problems, security issues that are currently occurring in Algeria and Sudan may also emerge in the future.

Although Arab countries are constantly looking for opportunities to attract more foreign investment, many foreign companies are reluctant to get caught in a bad Arab market vortex. The current trend of foreign capital is more inclined to detach from countries in distress, and domestic capital is actively flowing to safer foreign markets.

The importance of the research is to study the reality of foreign direct investment to the Arab countries during the period from 2000 to 2017 and to know the Arab countries most attractive to foreign direct investment and also the knowledge of countries expelling foreign direct investment and knowing the reasons that led to the increase or decrease of foreign direct investment in different Arab countries during the period of study and try to link between foreign direct investment and between political stability and the absence of terrorism.

The research content of this paper is divided into the following parts:

The first unit: Introduction research background and importance the second. unit will be about the methodology of this study, the third unit an analysis of data on foreign direct investment of the Arab countries during the study period from 2000 to 2017, the fourth one the knowledge of the link between foreign direct investment flows and the situation of political instability and the absence of violence the final one will be the conclusion

2. Research methods

3.

A foreign direct investment (FDI) is an investment in the form of a controlling ownership in a business in one country by an entity based in another country.[11] It is thus distinguished from a foreign portfolio investment by a notion of direct control. The origin of the investment does not impact the definition, as an FDI: the investment may be made either "inorganically" by buying a company in the target country or "organically" by expanding the

Broadly, foreign direct investment includes "mergers and acquisitions, building new facilities, reinvesting profits earned from overseas operations, and intra company loans". In a narrow sense, foreign direct investment refers just to building new facility, and a lasting management interest (10 percent or more of voting stock) in an enterprise operating in an economy other than that of the investor.[12] FDI is the sum of equity capital, long-term capital, and short-term capital as shown in the balance of payments. FDI usually involves participation in management, joint-venture, transfer of technology and expertise. Stock of FDI is the net (i.e., outward FDI minus inward FDI) cumulative FDI for any given period. Direct investment excludes investment through purchase of shares.[13]

FDI, a subset of international factor movements, is characterized by controlling ownership of a business enterprise in one country by an entity based in another country. Foreign direct investment is distinguished from foreign portfolio investment, a passive investment in the

securities of another country such as public stocks and bonds, by the element of "control".[1] According to the Financial Times, "Standard definitions of control use the internationally agreed 10 percent threshold of voting shares, but this is a grey area as often a smaller block of shares will give control in widely held companies. Moreover, control of technology, management, even crucial inputs can confer de facto control over operations of an existing business in that country.

According to Grazia Ietto-Gillies (2012),[14] prior to Stephen Hymer's theory regarding direct investment in the 1960s, the reasons behind Foreign Direct Investment and Multinational Corporations were explained by neoclassical economics based on macro-economic principles. These theories were based on the classical theory of trade in which the motive behind trade was a result of the difference in the costs of production of goods between two countries, focusing on the low cost of production as a motive for a firm's foreign activity. For example, Joe S. Bain only explained the internationalization challenge through three main principles: absolute cost advantages, product differentiation advantages and economies of scale. Furthermore, the neoclassical theories were created under the assumption of the existence of perfect competition. Intrigued by the motivations behind large foreign investments made by corporations from the United States of America, Hymer developed a framework that went beyond the existing theories, explaining why this phenomenon occurred, since he considered that the previously mentioned theories could not explain foreign investment and its motivations.

Hymer's importance in the field of International Business and Foreign Direct Investment stems from him being the first to theorize about the existence of Multinational Enterprises (MNE) and the reasons behind Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) beyond macroeconomic principles, his influence on later scholars and theories in International Business, such as the OLI (Ownership, Location and Internationalization) theory by John Dunning and Christos Pitelis which focuses more on transaction costs. Moreover, "the efficiency-value creation component of FDI and MNE activity was further strengthened by two other major scholarly developments in the 1990s: the resource-based (RBV) and evolutionary theories" (Dunning & Pitelis, 2008) [15] In addition, some of his predictions later materialized, for example the power of supranational bodies such as IMF or the World Bank that increases inequalities (Dunning & Pitelis, 2008).

The research methods will be based on the collection of data on foreign direct investment during the study period from 2000 to 2017. The analysis of the data through Microsoft Excel to determine the of the foreign direct investment curve for the Arab countries during the study

period and we will use the SPSS statistical analysis program to draw the forms of investment size Direct foreign investment for each country and to carry out the descriptive analysis of foreign direct investment data for Arab countries during the study period.

Then will make the comparison between the results of foreign direct investment of Arab countries and the state of political decision of the Arab countries and the absence of terrorism and is there relationship and impact of political stability and the absence of terrorism on foreign direct investment flows of various Arab countries

3. 1 FDI IN ARABIC COUNTRIES

The growth of foreign direct investment in the Arab world is weak, less than the level of global growth, and Arab countries are not considered attractive investment areas except for some countries that we will talk about later. As shown in Table 1, foreign direct investment of seventeen Arab countries there are Data available on the website of United Nations Conference on Trade and Development in 2000 about one billion three hundred and seventy-six million dollars and reached in 2016 to 19 billion and five hundred and thirty-five million dollars and an increase estimated by more than fourteen times, but this increase Still not the same of the increase of the global level of international investment flows. Table (1) and Figure (1) shows that foreign direct investment flows to Arab countries were very high in 2008, the year of the global financial crisis. To 55 billion, eight hundred and seventeen million dollars and is the largest inflow of foreign direct investment to Arab countries at all, and this amount is more than 40 times the amount that was in 2000, and this shows that

The global financial crisis has had a negative impact and long On the share of Arab countries in foreign investments The global financial crisis pushed to the local Investor search for new markets and places more safety for their investments and reinforced this more waves of violence and political instability that has occurred in the Arab countries, and especially after the events of the Arab Spring thinking. Before the global financial crisis, the annual increase in foreign direct investment was estimated at more than 60%. After the global financial crisis, it fell to less than 11%, from more than 55 billion dollars in the Arab countries in 2008 to less than 20%. Billion in

only eight years and if this deficit continues at the same pace, foreign direct investment will be less than zero in less than 10 years in Arab countries..

Figure 1 Foreign Direct Investment in the Arab World 2000 – 2016

Tab: 1 Foreign Direct Investment in the Arab World 2000 – 2016

year	country	Algeria	Bahrain	Comoros	Iraq	Egypt	Jordan	Kuwait	Lebanon	Mauritania	Morocco	Oman	Qatar	Saudi Arabia	SUDAN	Somalia	Tunisia	United Arab Emirates	Yemen	total
2000		280.1	363.5638	0.093636	-0.032	1235.4	913.2581	16.29981	993.475	40.096	421.9621	83.2	251.6	183	392.2	0.27	779.4671	-506.33	6.39951	5454.023
2001		1113.106	80.31915	1.145915	-6.656	509.9	273.6248	16.29981	1453.907	76.7	2807.06	5.2	295.52	504	574	0.04	486.547	1183.84	6.39951	9380.953
2002		1065	217.0213	0.430423	-0.326	646.9	238.2228	3.619445	1453.907	67.34035	480.6907	122	623.92	453	713.18	0.14	820.831	95.3	114.302	7115.479
2003		637.8812	516.7003	0.79376	1000	237.4	546.9676	-67.1114	2860.02	101.958	2314.468	25	624.92	778.4614	1349.19	-0.85	583.6425	4255.956	-89.107	15676.29
2004		881.8514	865.3082	0.671354	300	2157.4	936.8124	23.75297	2483.693	404.102	894.5627	111	1198.97	1942	1511.07	-4.79	639.1162	10003.5	143.578	24492.6
2005		1145.339	1048.67	0.558644	515.3	5375.6	1984.485	233.9041	3321.491	811.8692	1653.986	1538	2500	12097.33	1617.098	24	783.0866	10899.93	-302.057	45248.6
2006		1888.165	2914.894	0.826177	383	10042.8	3544.006	121.3057	3131.674	154.6016	2449.446	1597	3500	12097.33	1841.834	24	3307.989	12805.99	1120.98	60925.85
2007		1743.331	912.234	7.681736	971.8	11578.1	2622.144	111.5357	3375.981	139.3728	2804.501	3332	4700	24319	1504.38	141	1616.251	14186.52	917.299	74983.13
2008		2631.711	2638.298	4.631826	1855.7	9494.6	2826.255	-5.95176	4002.062	342.7707	2487.094	2952	3778.626	39456	1653.12	87	2758.615	5062.972	1554.62	83580.12
2009		2753.755	257.1809	13.78411	1598.3	6711.6	2413.099	1113.59	4378.908	-3.07204	1951.707	1485	8124.736	36458	1726.298	108	1687.811	1134.288	129.194	72042.18
2010		2301.226	155.8511	8.342262	1396.2	6385.6	1688.592	1304.626	3708.38	130.5284	1573.856	1243	4670.33	29233	2063.731	112	1512.505	8796.77	188.628	66473.16
2011		2580.354	98.40426	23.08816	1882.3	-483	1485.915	3259.067	3137.05	588.7496	2568.434	1628	938.5165	16308	1734.377	102	1147.907	7152.096	-518.42	43632.84
2012		1499.421	1545.213	10.41205	3400.4	6031	1548.31	2872.584	3111.318	1388.587	2728.361	1365.41	395.8791	12182	2311	107.33	1603.186	9566.651	-531	51136.06
2013		1684	3728.723	4.230442	-3119.8	4256	1946.761	1433.633	2661.096	1125.684	3298.102	1612.484	-840.385	8865	1687.884	258	1116.541	9764.915	-133.6	39349.27
2014		1506.733	1518.617	4.67833	10176.4	4612	2178.451	953.4815	2907.119	1125.684	3561.241	1287.386	1040.385	8012	1251.281	261	1063.805	11071.54	-233.105	31945.89
2015		-584	64.89362	5.146835	-7574.2	6925.2	1600.282	310.5494	2353.207	502.074	3254.8	-2171.65	1070.879	8141	1728.373	303	1002.74	8550.902	-15.445	25467.75
2016		1635	243.3510638	8.015624666	-6255.9	8106.8	1552.957746	418.7499586	2610.181957	271.1978174	2157.150314	-	773.9010989	7453	1063.767535	334	884.9955773	9604.773257	-561	28129.29046
total		24762.97	17169.24	94.53128	-13830.3	83823.3	28300.14	12119.93	47943.47	7268.243	37407.42	14043.38	33647.8	218482.1	24722.78	1856.14	21795.04	123629.6	1797.666	685033.5

The Arab countries are 22 countries that are close in terms of language, religion, customs and traditions. They are located in the western part of Asia. They are the Arabs of ASEAN, North Africa and the western part of the Red Sea. These countries differ in terms of size, regimes and economic power. Some Arab countries are among the poorest countries in the world and some of the richest countries in the world. Others suffer from political and security problems and others enjoy political and security stability. The study of foreign direct investment in general for all Arab countries does not give reliable information in general without looking at these differences does not give us the right view in the study of foreign direct investment and we will now offer a simple figures of foreign direct investment in various Arab countries, before we start showing the figures we want to point out, but some Arab countries were excluded for lack of availability Data for these countries and only the countries in which the data were recorded.

Table 1 and Figure 2 and 3 indicate that the Arab countries, without exception, were affected by the inflow of foreign direct investment to the global financial crisis. This negative impact was also uneven. It also appears that the oil countries are also affected by the flow of foreign direct investment to them by changing the price of oil Global.

Saudi Arabia is the largest economic country in the Middle East and the Arab region. It is the only Arab country that belongs to the 20 largest countries. This country accounts for more than 31% of the total investment in the Arab countries combined. This may be due to the strength of the Saudi economy. Is the first oil exporter in the world and provides multiple investment opportunities both in industry and tourism and other fields, and comes second in the United Arab Emirates with about 18% of the volume of foreign direct investment to all Arab countries and this comes back to the force Of the economy in the United Arab Emirates for several factors including oil production and also for foreign direct investment as the UAE is an active country in the field of real estate investment, which provides them with more foreign direct investment flows to the strategic location of the country, which lies between the Asian countries and African countries and proximity Relative to the European market, and the UAE is the largest open market for re-export in the region, and comes in third place, the Arab Republic of Egypt by 12% of the volume of foreign direct investment to Arab countries and this is due to the large Egyptian market and To tourism opportunities and Egypt is the most Arab countries in terms of population density and represents about 30% of the size of the population in the Arab countries, and then solve Lebanon and Morocco ... etc.

Iraq is considered to be the least country in the field of foreign direct investment. The total foreign direct investment inflows were negative. This means that even the local capital leaves the Iraqi territories to search for better commercial markets.

It is noteworthy that the six Gulf states, in addition to Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Oman, Qatar, Kuwait and Bahrain represent about 60% of the volume of foreign direct investment to all Arab countries, and this can return to the political stability and purchasing

power of the citizens of these countries as well Legal facilities related to foreign direct investment,

Figure 2 Foreign Direct Investment in the Arab World 2000 – 2016 by counties

Figure 3 shows the percentages for each country and effect relationship. Therefore, we analyze these relationships, so the failure propagation mechanism in the production process will be proposed in the next section.

3.2 Descriptive Statistics

We provided a descriptive analysis of the individual countries used in this study. Descriptive statistics provide a summary of what a research has found Range ,Minim ,Maximum ,Mean ,Means and standard deviation of all the countries provided. The following table 2, summarizes the descriptive statistics of the individual items of this study.

Tab: 2 Descriptive statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Algeria	17	3337.76	-584.00	2753.76	1456.6455	877.25143
Bahrain	17	3663.83	64.89	3728.72	1009.9554	1118.34701

Comoros	17	22.99	.09	23.09	5.5607	6.07238
Iraq	17	12061.10	-483.00	11578.10	4930.7824	3733.68204
Egypt	17	13576.80	-10176.40	3400.40	-813.5479	3742.03682
Jordan	17	3305.78	238.22	3544.01	1664.7142	907.60727
Kuwait	17	3326.18	-67.11	3259.07	712.9373	1015.45468
Lebanon	17	3385.43	993.48	4378.91	2820.2041	899.23216
Mauritania	17	1391.66	-3.07	1388.59	427.5437	436.60479
Morocco	17	3139.28	421.96	3561.24	2200.4367	937.19295
Oman	17	5503.65	-2171.65	3332.00	826.0810	1481.57018
Qatar	17	8965.12	-840.38	8124.74	1979.2822	2278.05696
Saudi Arabia	17	39273.00	183.00	39456.00	12851.8898	12501.37986
SUDAN	17	1918.80	392.20	2311.00	1454.2814	516.38255
Somalia	17	338.79	-4.79	334.00	109.1847	114.60404
Tunisia	17	2821.44	486.55	3307.99	1282.0610	762.15848
United Arab Emirates	17	14692.85	-506.33	14186.52	7272.3302	4576.52195
Yemen	17	2115.62	-561.00	1554.62	105.7450	583.51635

4. Political stability and the absence of violence

4.1 Indicators of political stability:

Political stability is the extent to which the political system is able to invest the conditions and its ability to deal successfully with crises to absorb the conflicts that are taking place within society, while not using violence, because violence is one of the most important phenomena of political

instability. Political stability is something sought by nations and peoples because it provides them with the atmosphere and environment necessary for security, development and prosperity. There are a number of indicators on which to calculate the political stability of a country, or not the most important

1 - the pattern of the transfer of power and the intention of the transfer of power represented by the head of state or government, a process that varies according to the type of political system and constitutional methods followed, if the transition process according to what is recognized by the constitution is a real indicator of the phenomenon of political stability, The way of coups and military intervention is a sign of political instability.

2 - The legitimacy of the political system is to justify the ruling power of the logic of collective will. That is, the political system acquires its legitimacy through the interests of the people and the maintenance of the independence of the country and the protection of rights ... This legitimacy is shown through the acceptance of the people of the regime and submission to them voluntarily. The refusal or involuntary acceptance of citizens, and the choice of patterns of power in society through free thought through participation and persuasion will lead to violence.

3 Institutionalism means that political decision-making in a society is governed by institutional mechanisms that take the system of separation of powers and respect for the law and away from the characterization of decision-making. The closer the political system approaches, the closer it is to stability, even if it is not democratic.

4. The strength of the political system and its ability to protect society and state sovereignty.

5 The limited change in the positions of political leaders, the survival of political leaders at the head of any political system for a long time indicator of political stability, but must be coupled with the consent of the people. A change in leadership positions is one of the indicators of instability

6 Parliamentary stability

Democracy and the consolidation of political participation and the free expression of citizens' views on national issues and the selection of deputies and representatives in the parliamentary and local councils. Public participation thus becomes a means of achieving internal stability and strengthening the law of political power

Second: Violence and security instability

The phenomenon of insecurity and the spread of violence in the Arab world is seen as a growing phenomenon in some Arab countries, especially those countries where there were protests after 2011 or the so-called Arab Spring countries in addition to Iraq while most Arab countries are witnessing a state of security stability and almost complete absence. And the phenomenon of terrorism, and despite the absence of violence and security stability in some Arab countries, some Arab countries remain in the middle of the relatively fragile institutions allows the recurrence of cases of violence and security instability unitary acceptance of citizens, and the choice of patterns of power in society through free thought through participation and persuasion will lead to violence.

The political decision-making in a society is governed by institutional mechanisms that take the system of separation of powers and respect for the law and away from the characterization of the decision-making process. The closer the political system is, the closer it is to stability, even if it is not democratic.

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4.2 Violence and security instability

The phenomenon of insecurity and the spread of violence in the Arab world is a growing phenomenon in some Arab countries, especially those countries where there were protests after 2011 or the so-called Arab Arab countries in addition to Iraq, while most Arab countries are witnessing a state of security stability and a near absence of violence. And the phenomenon of terrorism, and despite the absence of violence and security stability in some Arab countries,

some Arab countries remain in the middle, the presence of relatively fragile institutions allows the recurrence of cases of violence and security instability

4.3 The relationship between political stability and the absence of violence on the one hand and foreign direct investment in the Arab countries

It is noticeable that there is a close link between political stability and foreign direct investment in various Arab countries. We note that foreign direct investment in politically stable countries is more than politically unstable countries. For example, the six Gulf countries accounted for about 60% of foreign direct investment flows During the period from 2000 to 2016 and these countries are considered politically stable due to the system of government in addition to the good economic situation of these countries, while the middle countries are proven political stability such as Egypt, Tunisia and Sudan less than the countries of political stability and The politically unstable countries are the least attractive countries for foreign direct investment, as in Yemen, Somalia, Syria, Libya, etc.

And the security situation is considered coincidental to the political situation and accompanied by it may be political stability cause stability of the security situation and also the security situation cause for political stability and both cases affected on the flows of foreign direct investment to countries, in our case under study and the impact of political stability on investment effect on the flows Foreign direct investment has also affected the security situation on foreign direct investment flows in the Arab countries, in the countries where political stability has been absent and where violence has taken place, there are no more foreign direct investment in Libya and Syria. Direct foreign investment record negative number in Iraq, and decreased dramatically in Sudan, Yemen and other Arab countries

4. Conclusion

Foreign direct investment is one of the most important pillars of the economy in the countries and Arab countries in general are considered to be scarce countries in foreign direct investment flows and concentrated investment in rich and stable countries, and we found in our study a relationship between positive political stability and security on the one hand and foreign direct investment On the other hand, our study came out with important recommendations: The Arab countries should create an appropriate environment for investment in order to increase the flow of foreign investment to them and to preserve the local capital from traveling abroad and to adopt various methods for further political stability and fighting violence and terrorism. More foreign direct investment flows to Arab countries and no domestic capital outflow.

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Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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